

Vertical Farms for Urban Food Security

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Feeding the six billion people that would live in the cities by 2050 is a staggering challenge. Vertical farms are rising as a part of the solution. [Besides a host of environmental and social benefits, addressing urban food security, proponents tout, is the major benefit of vertical farms.](#) Growing high-quality vegetables with fewer inputs and greater yields for the nearby city-dwellers is welcome. But, how well do vertical farms contribute to urban food security?

Food security is a balance of four dimensions — physical **availability** of food, economic **access**, nutritional **utilization**, and the **stability** of the first three dimensions over time. Like a table, cut a leg short, food security will tumble to the ground. Understanding the role of vertical farms in urban food security needs a focused appraisal of vertical farms for each of these dimensions.

Availability

Availability is the physical presence and choices of food items in an area. Food availability relates directly to food production and trade aspects of a region. In a city, food is sourced through rural or international imports. The “just-in-time” food sourcing for perishable produce is efficient. But, transporting food thousands of miles is susceptible to unforeseen events leading to “food deserts” in the cities. Vertical farms in the cities can help mitigate these issues.

Vertical farms can churn out enormous crop volumes per acre of land compared to field production and increase the available produce in the cities. Vertical farms fall

short, however, with crop choices. Currently, only a select few high-value salad crops are grown in vertical farms and these crops cannot meet the caloric demands of the urban population. Efforts are underway to expand the crop selection for vertical farms to beans, tomatoes and berries. Even with the adoption of more crops and developments in technology, VFs could, at most, meet the vegetable requirements for part of the urban population. VF growing staple crops that form the bulk of caloric intake (rice, wheat) are still far off in the future, if ever.

Access

Availability of food alone does not ensure food security. If one cannot afford the available food, they will still go hungry. Economic access to food depends on the public income and food prices. The initial start-up, real-estate and energy costs for vertical farms are prohibitively high, and these farms have to make money to keep the lights on, quite literally, to produce food. Running a vertical farm can be economically viable only by growing high-value crops such as leafy greens and speciality herbs that fetch a fat profit margin. The produce from vertical farms, therefore, can be more expensive than field-grown crops.

Although the urban population, in general, has a higher buying power, there can be huge disparities in income among the urban population. Catering to the low-income section of the urban areas is, therefore, a challenge. The premium price tag makes VF produce less affordable to the people most susceptible to food insecurity. It is only until the drop in start-up and energy costs can vertical farms produce more crop varieties at a price comparable to their field-grown counterpart.

Utilization

Vertical farms mainly produce high-value leafy vegetables for their higher profit margin. Photo by [Jef Wright](#) on [Unsplash](#)

Food utilization refers to the proper biological use of food to meet the caloric and nutrient requirements. Utilization also closely ties in with nutritional quality and food safety. There is one aspect of food for which vertical farms are unrivalled: quality.

Vertical farms take advantage of the precise control of environmental factors to provide the optimal growth conditions for the crop. Picked at the right time, the vegetables grown under just the right balance of light, temperature, nutrients, and CO₂ in the vertical farms are of immensely superior nutritional quality and taste to their traditional counterparts. Also, because the crops in vertical farms are grown in a highly enclosed space, the chances of insect pest or disease attacks are almost nil. This means the shiny green salad leaves are untainted by harmful pesticides, herbicides, and antibiotics.

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Stability

Even if one can happily buy a hearty harvest of green goodness from the bountiful shelves of their local grocery store, they are still food insecure if food becomes unavailable or inaccessible even periodically. All three aspects of food security — availability, access, and utilization — have to persist over time to be considered truly food secure.

Adverse weather, pest and disease epidemics, political instability, and other unforeseen events — such as a global pandemic — can affect the stability of food availability and access in urban areas.

Being an enclosed controlled environment set up, vertical farms are rarely susceptible to weather changes. Snow or sunshine, these farms can keep churning out produce 365 days a year. Vertical farms can therefore contribute to a steady availability of produce in urban areas regardless of the weather.

Vertical farms are not completely immune to disruptions, though. These farms rely on water, fertilizers, and energy transported from distant places. Any disruption to the input supply chain can halt crop production altogether. Close attention should be paid to the input supply chain in the wake of disruptive events to mitigate the effects on food production in vertical farms.

Raising the bar

The constraints, such as high start-up costs, high energy requirements and limited crop types, are the major hurdles keeping the vertical farms from reaching their full potential in addressing urban food security. Technological advancement to introduce new crops and to further optimise growth conditions for existing crops is the way to go.

Vertical farms certainly cannot single-handedly ensure the food security of the urban population, as neither can traditional farming. It is, however, well suited to address multiple aspects of food security in urban areas. An added tool in the

toolbox, vertical farming complements the existing food systems to improve food security in urban areas.

There is ample room for improvement in the capabilities of vertical farms to address each dimension of urban food security. But, for now, vertical farms are already contributing to urban food security — and there is only up to go.